

DESIGN AND MANUFACTURING OF OPTIMUM VARIABLE STIFFNESS LAMINATES

K. Fayazbakhsh¹, M. Arian-Nik¹, D. Pasini^{1*}, L. Lessard¹, J. Chen² and A. Yousefpour²
¹ Mechanical Engineering, McGill University, Montreal, Canada, ² National Research Council
 Canada, Montreal, Canada

* Corresponding author (damiano.pasini@mcgill.ca)

Keywords: *Variable stiffness composites; Gap/overlap; Automated fiber placement*

Abstract

Variable stiffness design can improve structural performance of composite laminates. During the manufacturing of these laminates, defects in the form of gaps and overlaps appear in the laminates, thereby affecting their structural performances. The amount of defects in variable stiffness laminates depends on design and manufacturing parameters. In this paper, the amount of gaps and overlaps are obtained for 10 variable stiffness laminates selected from the Pareto front obtained for simultaneous maximization of in-plane stiffness and buckling load. The Defect Layer Method is then used to build the Finite Element model of the laminates and calculate the effect of defects on their structural performances. It is found that overlaps cause the Pareto front to shift towards higher values of in-plane stiffness and buckling load, whereas gaps decrease both design objectives. Two variable stiffness laminate design among the 10 under investigation were manufactured by National Research Council Canada and will be tested to verify the numerical results.

1 Introduction

The design of a laminated composite structure requires selecting the best arrangement of the constituent materials within the laminate. Traditionally, this task is performed by finding a combination of several straight-fiber layers, each with constant thickness, such that the combination provides the best mechanical properties for a given application. However, allowing the fibers to follow curvilinear paths within the plane of laminates constitutes an advanced tailoring option that can lead to modifications of load paths within the laminate, thereby resulting in a more favorable stress distribution and an improved structural performance. The former approach is referred as constant stiffness

design while the latter is called variable stiffness design [1].

Variable stiffness laminates can be manufactured by using Automated Fiber Placement (AFP) [2]. An AFP machine typically has a self-contained fiber placement head with three rotational degrees-of-freedom (DOF) mounted on a motion base with several translational DOFs. A mandrel with an additional rotational DOF provides a tool surface on which bands of prepreg strips (called courses) are placed. A course is typically made of 8-32 prepreg strips, called tows [3].

The improvement in in-plane stiffness and buckling load of variable stiffness design over constant stiffness has been demonstrated by several authors. Gurdal and Olmedo [4] suggested a linear fiber angle variation from one end of a plate to the other. They performed an analysis of in-plane stiffness variation and its effects on the elastic response of a plate. In another attempt, Olmedo and Gurdal [5] used the same fiber path model to investigate the buckling resistance of the plates under uniform compression. It was found that up to 80% increase in buckling load can be achieved compared to constant stiffness laminates. Tatting and Gurdal [6, 7] designed and manufactured flat plates with a linear fiber angle variation for maximum buckling load under shear loading. An improvement up to 224% in buckling load for variable stiffness design compared to a constant stiffness was found. In the previously mentioned research works, curvilinear fiber paths were found to substantially improve one of the properties under the investigation, whereas the other one was either deteriorated or remained constant. Since the concurrent improvement of buckling load and in-plane stiffness was not examined, the benefits of a variable stiffness design were not fully exploited.

Buckling load and in-plane stiffness are examples of two conflicting objectives that can be simultaneously maximized in the design of composite plates, a problem that falls within the area of multi-objective optimization. Instead of a single optimum solution, this problem has a set of optimum solutions defining the Pareto front, which represents the trade-offs among the objectives [8].

Among several design optimization algorithms, evolutionary strategies have been demonstrated to be capable of returning a population of solutions at each iteration of the optimization process. The Genetic algorithm (GA), which belongs to this category, has been widely used and recommended for optimizing composite structures [9]. The GA, however, being a population-based algorithm, requires a large number of function evaluations to reach the optimum solution. This requirement makes the process of finding an optimum solution computationally expensive. To overcome this issue, the coupling of a surrogate model with GA has been recognized as beneficial [10].

To manufacture plates with optimum variable stiffness plates, an AFP machine lays down the first course along the reference fiber path. Then, the machine head is offset to cover the whole plate. If the course width could change continuously, there would not be any defects. In practice, however, the course width can be changed only by a discrete value via either adding or dropping tows. Thus, small areas of triangular gaps and/or overlaps appear between adjacent courses. There are several strategies to drop the tows. 0% coverage (complete gap) is a strategy that involves dropping a tow as soon as one edge of the tow reaches the course boundary; it creates small triangular areas without fibers, i.e. gaps. The other method is 100% coverage (complete overlap); here, a tow is dropped when both edges of the tow cross the course boundary, thereby creating small areas of triangular overlaps. An intermediate scenario is when the coverage is between 0 and 100% [7]. Similar strategies can be followed to add the tows, which in turn results in the formation of gaps and/or overlaps.

Gaps are regions without fibers that are likely to be filled with resin during the curing process while overlaps are regions with thickness build-up. As a result, gap regions have lower stiffness compared to the regular composite material areas, while overlaps tend to generate stiffer-like features, which will

carry higher load compared to the regular composite material areas [6]. Several authors investigated the effect of gaps and/or overlaps on the mechanical properties of variable stiffness laminates manufactured by AFP machines. Wu and Gurdal [11] considered one variable stiffness design manufactured by two different techniques: tow drop (with 0% coverage), and overlap method. They investigated the structural response of variable stiffness panels subjected to thermal loads. Qualitative comparison of the bending strains for the two variable stiffness panels showed that the strain magnitudes are larger for a variable stiffness panel with overlaps. Wu et al. [12] extended the previous work and presented the structural response of the variable stiffness panels subjected to compression loads by mechanical end shortening. Results were compared to the response of a $[\pm 45]_{ss}$ cross-ply laminate (the baseline). Structural analyses have been performed using nonlinear shell analysis and the manufactured panels were also tested. Experimental results showed that prebuckling stiffness of the panel with overlap is 27% greater than the baseline, while it is only 4% higher for the panel with gaps. Numerical analyses showed that prebuckling stiffness and buckling load of the panels with overlaps are 35% and 119% greater than the baseline, respectively. The corresponding values for the panel with gaps showed 9% and 13% improvements in the prebuckling stiffness and buckling load, respectively. It should be noted that improvements in prebuckling stiffness and buckling load of the variable stiffness panel with gaps were obtained when the presence of gaps in the model is ignored. Tatting and Gurdal [6] and Jegley et al. [13] analyzed a rectangular flat panel with and without a central hole of varying size. The loading was introduced through a constant compressive displacement at the top edge and the vertical sides of the panel were constrained by knife-edge supports. They considered a constant stiffness $[\pm 45_2 / \pm 30 / \pm 45 / \pm 15]_s$ laminate as the baseline. For the best tow steered design, the buckling loads were increased by around 20% and 60% for the tow drop with 0% coverage and overlap methods, respectively. Both cases also exhibited relatively small degradation when holes were introduced. It should be noted that in the previously mentioned works, gaps were not modeled in the structural

analysis of variable stiffness laminates with tow drop. Blom et al. [14] investigated the influence of gaps on the strength and stiffness of variable stiffness laminates using Finite Element Method (FEM). They found that increasing the total gap area in the laminate deteriorates the strength and stiffness properties. In their work, the elements were assumed to be in areas filled with either regular composite material or resin only. One limitation of this method is that it requires the size of the elements to be small enough to capture precisely the gap areas. Therefore, the number of elements in the FE model drastically increases with the plate size, thereby resulting in a reduced computational efficiency. In addition, previous work in the literature considered tow drops during 0% coverage only, while the appearance of gaps can be avoided using tow drop with 100% coverage.

In this paper, 10 optimum variable stiffness laminates are selected and tow drop with 0% and 100% coverage considered as the manufacturing strategies to numerically investigate the effect of gaps and overlaps on their structural performance. Among them, two designs are manufactured to verify the numerical results.

2 Problem definition

A 0.254×0.4064 m (10×16 in) variable stiffness plate with $[\pm < T_1 | T_0 | T_1 >]_{4s}$ layup subjected to a uniform end shortening along the y-direction is considered as a case study. The transverse edges are considered free for in-plane displacement and all edges are simply supported against out of plane movement. $[< T_1 | T_0 | T_1 >]$ shows the layers in the laminate with variable fiber orientation according to a constant curvature path. The fiber orientation varies along x-direction (perpendicular to the loading direction) (Figure 1a) and can be formulated as

$$\cos(\varphi) = \cos(T_0) - \kappa |x|, \tag{1}$$

The fiber path can be shifted along y-direction to manufacture the entire plate (Figure 1b). Carbon epoxy Cytec® G40-800/5276-1 material properties used in this study are as follows: $E_x=143\text{GPa}$, $E_y=9.1\text{GPa}$, $G_{xy}=4.8\text{GPa}$ and $\nu_{xy}=0.3$ [15]. The thickness of each ply is assumed 0.159 mm (0.00625 in).

Fig. 1. (a) A composite lamina with a constant curvature fiber path; (b) fibers are offset along y-direction.

3 Methodology

A set of optimum solutions (Pareto front) is obtained by the simultaneous maximization of in-plane stiffness and buckling load using a Non-dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm-II (NSGAI) integrated with a surrogate model (Radial Basis Function) algorithm [10]. The results are shown in Figure 2, where the variable stiffness laminates have been assumed to be free of defects. In addition, the objective functions are normalized with respect to the corresponding values of a $[45/0/-45/90]_{2s}$ quasi-isotropic laminate.

Fig. 2. The Pareto front obtained without considering the effect of gaps and overlaps and 10 selected designs.

To manufacture the optimum designed laminates on the Pareto front, the AFP machine head places the first course along the reference fiber path. Then, the head is offset along the y-direction to place the

subsequent courses. During manufacturing, gaps and/or overlaps appear in the laminates and their extent can be controlled by the coverage percentage. In this study, 0% (complete gap) and 100% coverage (complete overlap) are investigated. MATLAB subroutines developed in [13] are used to locate gaps and overlaps, and calculate their area percentages. Then, a method, called defect layer method [13], is used to build the Finite Element (FE) model of variable stiffness laminates with defects and calculate their structural properties considering the effect of gaps and overlaps.

4 Results

Here, 10 designs on the Pareto front are selected to investigate the effect of gaps and overlaps on their performance, i.e. in-plane stiffness and buckling load (Figure 2). The Pareto points are selected in a way to have the maximum Euclidean distance from each other in the feasible design space; their laminate designs are tabulated in Table 1 along with their gap and overlap area percentages. It is assumed that a course with 8-tow each 3.175 mm (1/8) wide and a one-sided tow drop strategy with complete gap (0% coverage) and complete overlap (100% coverage) is used to manufacture the selected 10 designs.

Table 1. The 10 selected designs on the Pareto front

#	Layup	Gap area percentage	Overlap area percentage
1	$[\pm < 26 45 26 >]_{4S}$	10.21	8.93
2	$[\pm < 16 40 16 >]_{4S}$	11.48	10.40
3	$[\pm < 11 35 11 >]_{4S}$	12.96	11.59
4	$[\pm < 9 30 9 >]_{4S}$	13.94	12.00
5	$[\pm < 8 26 8 >]_{4S}$	13.17	11.94
6	$[\pm < 7 23 7 >]_{4S}$	13.84	11.94
7	$[\pm < 6 19 6 >]_{4S}$	13.12	11.81
8	$[\pm < 5 15 5 >]_{4S}$	12.89	11.56
9	$[\pm < 4 9 4 >]_{4S}$	11.20	10.42
10	$[0]_{4S}$	0	0

The defect layer method is used to build the FE model of the selected designs and obtain their in-plane stiffness and buckling load considering the effect of gaps and overlaps (Figure 3). Furthermore,

to compare plates' performance on an equal-weight basis, the in-plane stiffness and buckling load of each design manufactured with overlaps are divided by the plate weights to account for the weight penalty.

Fig. 3. Pareto fronts with and without considering the effect of defects.

As can be seen in Figure 3, overlaps cause a shift of the Pareto front towards higher values of in-plane stiffness and buckling load, whereas gaps has the effect of decreasing both design objectives. High improvements in in-plane stiffness and buckling load for the laminates with overlap are scaled down if the weight penalty is considered (labeled as modified complete overlap in Figure 2). There are no defects in the $[0]_{4S}$ laminate, which is a straight fiber design; as a result, this design in each Pareto front with and without defects shows no change in the normalized in-plane stiffness and buckling load. Ignoring the weight penalty for the laminates with overlap results in higher in-plane stiffness than the $[0]_{4S}$ laminate for the $[\pm < 4 | 9 | 4 >]_{4S}$ laminate, which has 10.42% overlaps. However, considering the weight penalty, the $[0]_{4S}$ laminate has the maximum in-plane stiffness. The $[\pm < 26 | 45 | 26 >]_{4S}$ laminate has the maximum improvement in buckling load, which is 56% higher than the baseline, where defects are ignored. For the laminates with overlap, there is 105% improvement in buckling load and this improvement is scaled down to 89% if the weight penalty is factored in. Gaps reduced the

improvement in buckling load caused by fiber steering from 56% to 40%.

As can be observed in Figure 3, the amount of change in in-plane stiffness and buckling load due to the presence of gaps and overlaps varies among the 10 selected designs. We observe that the change is a function of gap and overlap area percentages. Other factors, such as the extent and location of gaps and overlaps, might also play a role.

In Figure 3, the Pareto fronts for the laminates with gaps and overlaps are obtained assuming that a course with 8 tows each 3.175 mm (1/8 in) wide was used for the designs' manufacturing. The manufacturing parameters, e.g. the number of tows inside each course and the tow width change the amount of defects emerging in variable stiffness laminates. Consequently, the change in in-plane stiffness and buckling load of the laminates considering the effect of gaps and overlaps will not be aligned with those found in Figure 3. Regarding the manufacturing parameters, an AFP machine can lay down 8, 12, 16, 24, and 32 tows inside each course and the tow width can have a value of 3.175 mm (1/8 in), 6.350 mm (1/4 in), and 12.70 mm (1/2 in). Here for the $[\pm < 26 | 45 | 26 >]_{45}$ laminate, which has the maximum improvement in buckling load, the effect of the number of tows and the tow width on in-plane stiffness and buckling load is investigated.

First, the number of tows inside each course is let to vary between 8 and 32, while the tow width is kept constant as 3.175 mm (1/8 in). The change in in-plane stiffness and buckling load for the case of gaps and overlaps are presented in Tables 2 and 3, respectively.

Table 2. Change in in-plane stiffness and buckling load for $[\pm < 26 | 45 | 26 >]_{45}$ laminate with gaps.

Number of tows	Tow width (in)	Gap area percentage	Change in in-plane stiffness (%)	Change in buckling load (%)
8	1/8	10.21	-14.88	-10.42
12	1/8	6.65	-9.91	-6.69
16	1/8	5.16	-7.82	-5.38
24	1/8	3.52	-5.50	-3.79
32	1/8	2.65	-4.29	-3.16

Table 2 shows that as the number of tows inside each course increases, the gap area percentage and

the amount of change in both laminate properties are reduced.

Table 3. Change in in-plane stiffness and buckling load for $[\pm < 26 | 45 | 26 >]_{45}$ laminate with overlaps.

Number of tows	Tow width (in)	Gap area percentage	Change in in-plane stiffness (%)	Change in buckling load (%)
8	1/8	8.93	9.85	31.58
12	1/8	5.88	6.31	20.23
16	1/8	4.40	4.72	14.98
24	1/8	3.02	3.27	10.20
32	1/8	2.41	2.62	7.75

In the case with overlaps, an increase in the number of tows in each course has the effect of reducing the overlap area percentage and the change in in-plane stiffness and buckling load.

In the next step, for the same laminate, the number of tows inside each course is kept constant as 8 and the tow width varies from 3.175 mm (1/8 in) to 6.350 mm (1/4 in) and 12.70 mm (1/2 in). The change in in-plane stiffness and buckling load for the case of gaps and overlaps are presented in Tables 4 and 5, respectively.

Table 4. Change in in-plane stiffness and buckling load for $[\pm < 26 | 45 | 26 >]_{45}$ laminate with gaps.

Number of tows	Tow width (in)	Gap area percentage	Change in in-plane stiffness (%)	Change in buckling load (%)
8	1/8	10.21	-14.88	-10.42
8	1/4	9.82	-13.11	-10.38
8	1/2	9.83	-12.74	-12.06

As can be seen in Table 4, the gap area percentage first decreases and then slightly increases for increasing the tow width. The laminate manufactured with a tow width of 1/2 in has the smallest reduction in in-plane stiffness and at the same time it has the highest drop in buckling load. Therefore, it can be concluded that the amount of defects is not the only parameter that plays a role in structural performance of the laminates.

Table 5. Change in in-plane stiffness and buckling load for $[\pm < 26 | 45 | 26 >]_{4s}$ laminate with overlaps.

Number of tows	Tow width (in)	Gap area percentage	Change in in-plane stiffness (%)	Change in buckling load (%)
8	1/8	8.93	9.85	31.58
8	1/4	5.88	6.31	20.23
8	1/2	4.40	4.72	14.98

From Table 5, we observe that by increasing the tow width, overlap area percentage and the change in in-plane stiffness and buckling load decrease.

5 Manufacturing Variable Stiffness Laminates

To simulate the fiber paths of the variable stiffness laminates, the ACE V2 software package is used. The ACE V2 generates the fiber paths and simulates the distribution of gaps and overlaps (Figure 4), as well as potential areas that may have quality problems due to minimum radius of curvatures of the fibers.

Fig. 4. ACE V2 simulation results, (a) Complete gaps; (b) Complete overlaps.

As it can be seen in Figure 4, there are no red areas in the laminate, which shows that the design meets the manufacturing constraint. Among the 10 designs on the Pareto front obtained earlier in Section 3, the $[\pm < 26 | 45 | 26 >]_{4s}$ and $[\pm < 16 | 40 | 16 >]_{4s}$ laminates are selected for manufacturing. The former offers the maximum achievable buckling load and is chosen to evaluate the real improvement in buckling

load after considering the effect of gaps or overlaps. The latter, which offers higher buckling load and the same in-plane stiffness of the baseline, is chosen to evaluate the effect of gaps or overlaps on both the design objectives.

A Viper 4000 fiber placement machine is used in the study to manufacture the designed laminates. This AFP machine has the capability to layup any even number of slit tape (1/8 inch width) up to 32 tows. To build a laminate with variable stiffness, each course in the AFP process is laid down by following a predefined curvilinear fiber path. Due to the fiber steering, gaps and/or overlaps are unavoidable in the laminates. To meet the design requirements, four laminates with full gaps and overlaps are manufactured (Figure 5).

Figure 5. The manufactured laminate with full gap strategy.

The individual tow cut/restart feature of the fiber placement machine makes it possible to distribute the gaps and overlaps across the laminates, as shown in Figure 6.

Fig. 6. Manufacturing of composite laminates by AFP

The prepreg slit tape used for making the test panels is Carbon/Epoxy from Cytec Engineered Materials. Before the layup process, the flat tool is prepared by placing a layer of peel ply onto the tool surface. Trials are conducted to optimize the processing parameters for manufacturing the composite panels with curvilinear fibers. After layup, the panels are bagged and cured in an autoclave at the temperature of 350°F and pressure of 85 psi for two hours. The panels are currently being tested to validate numerical results presented in this paper.

6 Conclusions

In this paper, the effect of gaps and overlaps on in-plane stiffness and buckling load of 10 variable stiffness laminates has been investigated. These designs were selected from the Pareto front obtained for simultaneous maximization of in-plane stiffness and buckling load. The modified Pareto fronts considering the presence of defects have been obtained to provide design guidelines of direct interest to industry. It is found that overlaps cause a shift of the Pareto front towards higher values of in-plane stiffness and buckling load, whereas gaps reduce both design objectives. With reference to the designs investigated in this paper, it is found that an improvement of up to 56% in buckling load can be obtained using the fiber steering capability of an AFP machine. In practice, this improvement increases to 105% when the effect of overlaps is modeled, whereas gaps decrease the improvement to 40%. For a particular variable stiffness laminate, we have found that by increasing the course width, the amount of defects and the change in in-plane stiffness and buckling load reduces. Future work is required to obtain modified Pareto fronts by incorporating the effect of defects during

the optimization process. Furthermore, other structural properties, like strength and fundamental frequency along with different loading and boundary conditions can be studied.

References

- [1] Ghiasi H, Fayazbakhsh K, Pasini D, Lessard L. Optimum stacking sequence design of composite materials Part II: Variable stiffness design. *Composite Structures*. 2010;93:1-13.
- [2] Evans DO, Vaniglia MM, Hopkins PC. Fiber placement process study. 34th International SAMPE Symposium and Exhibition. Reno, Nevada; USA;1989. p. 1822-33.
- [3] Gürdal Z, Tatting BF, Wu KC. Tow-placement technology and fabrication issues for laminated composite structures. 46th AIAA/ASME/ASCE/AHS/ASC Structures, Structural Dynamics & Materials Conference. Austin, Texas, 2005. p. 1-17.
- [4] Gürdal Z, Olmedo R. In-plane response of laminates with spatially varying fiber orientations: variable stiffness concept. *AIAA journal*. 1993;31:751-8.
- [5] Olmedo R, Gürdal Z. Buckling response of laminates with spatially varying fiber orientations. American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics, S. W, Washington, D. C. 20024-2518, USA; 1993. p. 2261-9.
- [6] Tatting BF, Gürdal Z. Design and manufacture of elastically tailored tow placed plates. NASA contractor report no NASA/CR-2002-211919. 2002.
- [7] Tatting BF, Gürdal Z. Automated finite element analysis of elastically-tailored plates. NASA contractor report no NASA/CR-2003-212679. 2003.
- [8] Deb K. Multi-objective optimization using evolutionary algorithms: Wiley, 2001.
- [9] Ghiasi H, Pasini D, Lessard L. Optimum stacking sequence design of composite materials Part I: constant stiffness design. *Composite Structures*. 2009;90:1-11.
- [10] Arian Nik M, Fayazbakhsh K, Pasini D, Lessard L. Surrogate-based multi-objective optimization of a composite laminate with curvilinear fibers. *Composite Structures*. 2012;94:2306-13.
- [11] Wu KC, Zafer G. Thermal Testing of Tow-Placed, Variable Stiffness Panels. NASA Langley Technical Report Server; 2001.

- [12] Wu KC, Gürdal Z, Starnes Jr J. Structural response of compression-loaded, tow-placed, variable stiffness panels. Proceedings of the AIAA/ASME/ASCE/AHS/ASC 43rd Structures, Structural Dynamics and Materials Conference, Denver, CO2002. p. 2002-1512.
- [13] Jegley DC, Tatting BF, Gürdal Z. Optimization of elastically tailored tow placed plates with holes. Proceedings of the AIAA/ASME/ASCE/AHS/ASC 44th Structures, Structural Dynamics and Materials Conference, Norfolk, VA: Citeseer; 2003. p. 2003-1420.
- [14] Blom AW, Lopes CS, Kromwijk PJ, Gürdal Z, PP C. A theoretical model to study the influence of tow-drop areas on the stiffness and strength of variable-stiffness laminates. *Comp Matls.* 2009;43:403-25.
- [15] CYCOM 5276-1® In: Inc. CEM, editor. New Jersey, USA.